
THE EFFECT OF PROMOTION AND PRODUCT QUALITY THROUGH PURCHASE DECISION ON THE CUSTOMER SATISFACTION OF BOHEMIAN PROJECT.ID PRODUCTS

Haikal Aulia Rahman, Arifin Sitio

*1 Universitas Mercubuana

Abstract:

This study aims to determine the effect of promotion and product quality through purchase intention on customer satisfaction of Bohemianproject.id products. The research conducted in Bandung on SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises) named Bohemianproject.id. Research data is primary data from questionnaires and secondary data. The sampling method used was probability sampling. Questionnaires were distributed to 100 customers who had purchased Bohemian project. id's products. The analytical method used is the path analysis method. The results showed that promotion, product quality through purchase intention are having a significant influence on product customer satisfaction from Bohemianproject.id. In-depth research in other business fields can be done to ensure other variables that affect customer satisfaction, this can help SMEs to make strategies and reduce failure to build a business.

Keywords: Promotion; Product Quality; Purchase Decision; Customer Satisfaction.

Cite This Article: Haikal Aulia Rahman Arifin Sitio. (2019). "THE EFFECT OF PROMOTION AND PRODUCT QUALITY THROUGH PURCHASE DECISION ON THE CUSTOMER SATISFACTION OF BOHEMIAN PROJECT.ID PRODUCTS." *International Journal of Engineering Technologies and Management Research*, 6(1), 55-72. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2555331.

1. Introduction

As a Small and Medium Enterprises (SME/UKM) engaged in the creative industry matters, Bohemian project.id continues to innovate. The open and wide market that are exist both here and abroad happens by the rise of science and technology, making everything easy and convenience. Bohemian project.id is an SME in the creative industry business of the craft subsector which have an enormous potential seen from the market perspective, as craft is on the TOP 3 of GDP producer in the creative economy of Indonesia.

Figure 1: Contribution of Creative Economy on GDP According to Subsectors Source: Bekraf RI

As craft being included in the Top 3 of GDP Ekraf should automatically open up the market for the SMEs that engaged in craft, but in contrary it is not the case for bohemian project.id on its report in 2016-2017 the revenue targeted by the bohemian is not in accordance with the income received.

Table 1: Annual Turnover Data of 2016-2017

FY	2016	2017
Target	Rp. 240,000,000	Rp. 240,000,000
Result	Rp. 78.950,000	Rp. 102,400,000
VS BP	32,8%	42,6%
Growth		9,8%

Source: Secondary data from Bohemianproject.id (2018)

According to the table above in the last 2 years, the sales turnover did not reach the target, even though there was an increase from 2016. This became the concern of the researcher, why did the turnover had not met the target amidst the broad market of creative economy both domestic and abroad. The researcher included several variables in this study which consisted of independent variables, intervening variables as well as dependent variables. Within this study the researcher will examine buyer decisions and customer satisfaction of bohemiantproject.id through independent variables such as promotion and product quality. One idea emerges in the context of renewal of the business strategy is to change the company's point of view in interpreting and maximizing their promotional strategies in order to reach a wider market, and to see the effects of promotion and product quality through buyer decision process and customer satisfaction from bohemianproject.id

Based on the conditions above, it will become the main idea in conducting this research. In addition to that, the author would further verify the results of previous studies therefore will be able to decide wether promotion and quality of products is an important part for developing the company. As a company that engaged in the creative economy sector, bohemian project.id must look for new ways that are in accordance with the development of science and technology of today to maximize

the company promotions and to maximize the resources they have to produce a sense of competitiveness that will significantly affects the decisions and satisfaction of the customers. Therefore, this study shall be titled "The Effect of Product Promotion and Quality through Purchasing Decisions on Bohemian Project.ID Products".

2. Theoretical Review

2.1. Purchase Decision

Purchase decision is the process of integration which combines knowledge to evaluate two or more alternative behavior therefore to produce a choice which is presented cognitively as a desire to behave by choosing one of the alternative choices available. Consumer's purchase decision making is a problem-solving process that is directed to the target. A purchase decision process involves several decisions.

According to Schiffman and Kanuk (2008: 43) purchase decision is the process of choosing two or more alternative choices that resulted in a decision to buy or not to buy. Alternative choices must be available when consumers will make their decision. The process of purchasing decision requires a different search or receipt of information.

2.2. Promotion

According to Tjiptono (2008: 219): "In the essence, promotion is a form of marketing communication". The definition of marketing communication is a marketing activity that seeks to spread out information, influence / persuade, and / or to remind the target of the company and its products for them to be willing to accept, buy, and be loyal to the products offered by the company. Furthermore, Kotler (2014: 41) stated that "Promotion is a variety of activities conducted by company which highlight the features of their products in order to persuade the target consumers to buy the products.

2.3. Product Quality

The quality level of a company's product is determined by the level of satisfaction of its consumer after or while consuming the product. According to Cannon, Perreault, and McCarthy (2009: 45) product quality is the product's ability to satisfy the customer needs or desires. Thus the level of product quality is directly proportional to the level of satisfaction and the level of consumer purchase decision. The concept of quality is often considered as a relative measure of benefit of a product or service that consists of quality of design and quality of conformance. The quality of design is regarding the function of the product specifications, while the quality of conformance is a measure of how far a product can meet the specified requirements and specifications (Tjiptono, 2008).

2.4. Customer Satisfaction

Lovelock (2012: 60) stated, that satisfaction is a kind of behavioral assessment which occurs after the experience of consuming a service. Most research agreed that confirmation or disconfirmation

of preconsumption expectations is a determining factor of satisfaction. This means that customers have certain predictions about the level of service they will receive in their minds before consuming the product. This particular level of prediction is usually the result of the search and selection process, when the customers decide to purchase a particular service. During the service process, the customers will experience service delivery and compare it with the service level they have predicted. Satisfaction assessment is then formed based on this comparison.

Thinking Framework

Figure 2: Thinking Framework

Source: Data Processing (2018)

3. Methods

3.1. Design and The Type of The Study

For this study, the data was processed using statistical methods through SPSS for Windows 23. The data analysis method used in this study consisted of three stages, which are several kinds of research tests, stage of regression analysis and correlation between dimensions.

3.2. Variables and Measurements

The independent variables of this study are promotion (X1), product quality (X2), the intervening variable is the purchase decision (Y) and the dependent variable is customer satisfaction (Z)

3.3. Types and Sources of Data

The data used in this study are quantitative. Quantitative data is a type of data that can be measured or calculated directly, in the form of information or explanations presented in numbers. In this case the quantitative data needed were: the number of consumers, and the results of the questionnaire. In this study the authors used two data sources, namely:

- Primary data sources, data were collected directly by the researcher (or officers) from the main source. The primary data source in this study is the results of the consumers of craft products questionnaire from bohemian project.id.
- Secondary data sources, the data were directly collected by the researcher to support the primary data. In other word, were data that is retrived in the form of documents. In this study, sales data is a secondary souce of data

3.4. Population and Sample

The population of this study are consumers of the craft products produced by bohemian project.id who have bought the products bohemian project.id. The classifications used in determining the samples are as follows:

- 1) Samples are consumers of bohemian project.id;
- 2) Samples have made purchases at least once during the last three months;
- 3) Samples are male and female;
- 4) The sample is over 17 years old.

Table 2: Operational Definiton

Variable	Dimensions		Indicators	
Purchase Decision (Y) Kotler (2009)	1	Stability of the product	a	Constancy of needs for the product to be purchased
	2	Constancy in buying the product	a	Constancy of buying certain product or brand
	3	Recommending to others	a	Willing to provide recommendations to other people to buy a certain product
Promotion (X1) Kotler and Keller (2007: 272)	1	Promotion Frequency	a	The number of sales promotions conducted at a period of time through sales promotion media
	2	Promotion Quality	a	Measurement of how well the sales promotion is done.
	3	Promotion Quantity	a	Value or number of sales promotions given by consumers.
	4	Period of The Promotion	a	The length of promotion carried out by the company.
	5	Accuracy of promotional goals	a	Factors needed to achieve the desired target of the company.
Product Quality (X2) Tjiptono (2012:170)	1	Performance	a	basic operating characteristics of a product.
	2	Durability	a	how long the product lasts before the product has to be replaced
			b	the higher the frequency of consumer usage of the product, the better the durability of the product
	3	Compliance	a	the extent to which the basic operating characteristics of a product meet the specifications
			b	Flawless product
	4	Features	a	product characteristics which designed to enhance the product function
			b	Increase the consumer interest in the product.

	5	Reliability	a	the probability that the product will provide satisfaction or not for a certain period of time		
			b	The less likely the occurrence of damage is, then the product is reliable.		
	6	Aesthetics	a	related to how the product looks		
			7	Impression of Quality	a	is the result of using measurements made indirectly for a possibility that consumers do not understand
	8	<i>Serviceability</i>	b	information on the product.		
			a	speed		
Consumer's Satisfaction Tjiptono (2004:101)	1	Conformity Expectation of	a	Products are in accordance with or exceed expectations		
			2	Repurchase	b	Desire to revisit because of the value and benefits of the products
			3	Willingness to Recommend	c	Recommendation for friends or relatives to buy the products because of the value and benefits

Source: Processed Data (2018)

3.5. Data Analysis Techniques

In this study, the data was processed using statistical methods through SPSS for Windows 23. The data analysis method used in this study consisted of three stages, which are several kinds of research tests, stage of regression analysis and correlation between dimensions

1) Data Quality Tests

Data quality testing was processed in 2 stages:

- **Validity test**

A validity test is used to determine whether a questionnaire is valid or not. A questionnaire is said to be valid if the question in the questionnaire is able to reveal something that is measured by the questionnaire itself (Sugiyono, 2015: 228).

- **Reliability Test**

Reliability or the level of reliability, accuracy or consistency is the research instruments' level of ability to collect data consistently from a group of individuals. The instrument reliability test is utilized to determine the consistency of the measuring instrument per their assignment, or whether the measuring instrument has a consistent results, if were to used several times in different times. The reliability test for this questionnaire was tested multiple times during different times, and the reliability test for this questionnaire was done through the Cronbach test (alpha) where an instrument can be considered reliable, (Ghozali, 2011: 48).

2) Descriptive Statistic

According to Ghozali (2013: 42) Descriptive statistic is utilized to provide a description of a data that is seen from the mean value, standard deviation, maximum, and minimum. According to Sugiyono (2012: 12) Descriptive statistic is statistic used to analyze a data that has been retrieved as it is without intending to create conclusions which applied to generally or generalizations.

3) Method of Successive Interval (MSI)

The data obtained as a result of the distribution of the questionnaire are ordinal, therefore in order for the analysis to be continued, the measurement scale must be raised to a higher measurement level, which is the scale of interval measurement so that it will be able to processed further. For this reason, the Method of Successive Interval (MSI) was applied (Riduwan, kuncoro (2017: 30), which is basically a procedure for placing each object into an interval.

4) Model Statistics Testing

A hypothesis testing was conducted in order to find out whether what is made in describing the correlation between variables is in line to the problems studied and the results of the analysis. Hypothesis testing is divided into:

- First Stage of hypothesis Model Feasibility Testing (Test F)
- Second Stage of Hypothesis Model Feasibility Testing (Test F)
- Coefficient of Determination (R2 Test)
- Partial Test (t test)

4. Results and Discussion

In this study, path analysis method was applied along with research variables including promotion (X1), product quality (X2), purchase decision (Y), and customer satisfaction (Z).

This sub-chapter of results of the study will describe the results of the questionnaires which have been processed through the SPSS program (Statistical Product and Service Solution). The results of this particular study will includes validity and reliability test results of the research instrument test, the descriptive research analysis, verificative analysis which were a path analysis of the coefficient correlation testing, the coefficient of determination hypothesis testing as well as direct and indirect influence. After describing the results of the study through SPSS, the researcher will also describe the general description of the bohemianproject.id product which is the object of this research.

4.1. Data Quality Test

Table 3: Validity Test Results of Customer Satisfaction Instruments (Z)

Correlations				
		r hitung	r tabel	Kesimpulan
Customer Satisfaction_25	Pearson Correlation	0,825	0,195	Valid
Customer Satisfaction_26	Pearson Correlation	0,859	0,195	Valid

Customer Satisfaction_27	Pearson Correlation	0,843	0,195	Valid
--------------------------	---------------------	-------	-------	-------

Source: Processed Data2018

Table 4: Promotion Variable Questionnaire Reliability Test Results

Reliability Statistics			
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items	Critical Point	Conclusion
0,828	5	0,70	Reliabel

Source: Processed Data 2018

Descriptive Statistic Analysis Results

Table 5: Statistical Analysis Results

No	Variable	Mean	Explanation
1	Promotion	78,40	Good
2	Product Quality	78,55	Good
3	Purchase Decision	65,00	Good
4	Customer Satisfaction	80,80	Very Good

Source: Processed Data 2018

Results of Classical Assumptions Test Analysis Substructure I

Normality Test

The data normality testing was done using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistics which was by testing the residual value of the regression results. The basis of decision making for the K-S test was based from the probability number, with the premis of if the probability is <0.05 then Ha is accepted and Ho is rejected, while if the probability is > 0.05 then it is Ha rejected and Ho accepted. The results of Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistics testing are as follows:

Table 6: Normality Test Result

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
	Unstandardized Residual	
N	100	
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	,0000000
	Std. Deviation	1,40154785
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	,081
	Positive	,056
	Negative	-,081
Test Statistic	,081	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	,103 ^c	
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		
c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.		

Source: Output SPSS 23, Processed Data (2018)

According to the SPSS output above, the Asymp value was Sig. (2-tailed) >alpha (5%) which is (0.103 ≥ 0.05), we can concluded that the data had normal distribution.

Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity test was required to test whether the regression model found a correlation between the independent variables. In an adequate model of regression I there should be no correlation between the independent variables. To detect the presence or absence of multicollinearity in the regression model was seen from the Tolerance Value or Variance Inflation Factor (VIF).

Table 7: Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficients ^a		
Variable	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Promotion	,474	2,109
Product quality	,474	2,109

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase decision

Source: Output SPSS 23, Processed Data (2018)

The results above indicates that each of the VIF value was less than the value of VIF variable far below 10. It is then can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity between the independent variables in the path analysis model.

Heterocedasticity Test

The heterocedasticity tests was conducted to test whether the variance of the residual observations is equal to each other or not. If in case the residual has the same variance, then it is shall be heteroscedasticity. Or heteroscedasticity occurs when the confounding variable (error) does not have the same variant for all observations. The data heterocedasticity testing was performed using the Scatterplot test. In the following it is presented the results of heteroscedasticity of the Scatterplot test method using the SPSS program.

The results of heteroscedasticity tests show that there is no breach of heteroscedasticity assumption within the path analysis model.

4.2. Hypothesis Test Results

Coefficient Correlation Test

Table 8: Coefficient Correlation Structure I

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,871 ^a	,758	,753	1,41592

a. Predictors: (Constant), Product quality, Promotion

b. Dependent Variable: Purchase decision

Source: Processed Data (2018)

Based on the results of data processing it was retrieved that R is 0.871, which means that the promotion variable and product quality have a very strong correlation with the purchase decision of bohemianproject.id product. The correlation occurs is a positive coefficient which translated to strong influence, which is between 0.800-1,000.

Coefficient of Determination Test

Based on the table containing the results of the data processing shows the coefficient of determination (RSquare) of 0.758 or 75.8%. This means that the percentage of contribution of promotion and product quality variables on the ups and downs of the purchase decision variable is 75.8% and the remaining 24.2% is the contribution of other variables not included in this study. (error1 = 0.242).

Simultaneous Test (F Test) Structure I

The simultaneous test was conducted to determine whether there is a simultaneous strong influence between promotion and product quality on purchase decision. Which can be seen in the table:

Table 9: F Test Structure I

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	608,916	2	304,458	151,862	,000 ^b
Residual	194,469	97	2,005		
Total	803,386	99			
a. Dependent Variable: Purchase decision					
b. Predictors: (Constant), Product quality, Promotion					

Source: Processed Data (2018)

Based on the results of the processing, the result of the F-count is 151,862. On the F-test table for 5% of significance level and the degree of freedom with $(n - (k + 1)) = 100 - (2 + 1) = 97$, as well as $F_{table} = 3.090$. Because F count is $\geq F_{table}$ or $151,862 \geq 3,090$ and sig F is 0,000, a decision can be made to reject H0. This means that there is a simultaneous significant effect between promotion and product quality on the purchase decision of bohemianproject.id product.

Partial Test (t Test) Structure I

A partial testing was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of the promotion and product quality variables on the purchase decision variables. This test was processed by the t test, the results are as follows:

Table 10: Path Coefficient and Partial Test (t test) structure I

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-2,899	,782		-3,707	,000
Promotion	,228	,060	,277	3,815	,000

Product quality	,183	,020	,649	8,943	,000
a. Dependent Variable: Purchase decision					

Source: Processed Data (2018)

From the results of data processing measures for the path analysis, the coefficients used are beta coefficients or standard coefficients (beta Standardized Coefficients). The rejection criteria of H0, if the t count is greater than the t table.

- 1) The first path coefficient = 0.277. The tcount was 3.815 by taking the significance level α of 0.05, the value of the t table = 1.985, therefore because t arithmetic = 3.815 is bigger than t table = 1.985, leads to rejection of H0 or in other words promotion affects the purchase decision with a path coefficient of 0.277.
- 2) The second path coefficient = 0.649. the tcount retrieved was 8.943 by taking a significance level of α of 0.05 , the value of t table = 1.985, and because the t arithmetic = 8.943 is bigger than the t table = 1.985, H0 is rejected or in other words the product quality affects the purchasing decision with a path coefficient of 0.649.

Table11: Variables Correlation Matrix of X1, and X2

Correlations				
		Purchase decision	Promotion	Product quality
Pearson Correlation	Purchase decision	1,000	,747	,849
	Promotion	,747	1,000	,725
	Product quality	,849	,725	1,000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Purchase decision	.	,000	,000
	Promotion	,000	.	,000
	Product quality	,000	,000	.
N	Purchase decision	100	100	100
	Promotion	100	100	100
	Product quality	100	100	100

Source: Processed Data (2018)

Based on the calculation, it was obtained the number of correlations between promotion variables and product quality of 0.725. which translated to the correlation between promotion and product quality variables is strong and positive, this can also be interpreted as the better the promotion, the higher the product quality will be, and vice versa.

Table 12: Direct and Indirect Effects of Promotion (X1) and Product quality (X2) on Purchase decision (Y)

Variable	Path Coefficient	Direct Effect (%)	Indirect effect(through), in %		Indirect Effect (%)	Total (%)
			X1	X2		
X1	0,277	7,66	-	13,02	13,02	20,68
X2	0,649	42,09	13,02	-	13,02	55,11
Total						75,8

Source: Processed Data (2018)

- 1) Promotion (X1) has a significant positive effect on purchase decision (Y) dominated by indirect effects.
- 2) Product Quality (X2) has a significant positive effect on purchase decisions (Y) dominated by direct effects.

Classical Assumption Test Substructure II

Classical Assumption test substructure II was done by the same method with the classic assumption substructure I test which is by normality test, multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity test.

Table 13: Normality Test Substructure II

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		100
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	,0000000
	Std. Deviation	1,19615700
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	,071
	Positive	,061
	Negative	-,071
Test Statistic		,071
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,200 ^{c,d}
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		
c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.		
d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.		

Source: Processed Data (2018)

From the SPSS output above, the Asymp value is obtained. Sig. (2-tailed) \geq alpha (5%) ie (0.200 \geq 0.05), which shows that the data is normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 14: Multicolinerity Test

Coefficients^a			
Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	Promotion	,412	2,426
	Product quality	,260	3,848
	Purchase decision	,242	4,131
a. Dependent Variable: Customer satisfaction			

Source: Processed Data (2018)

The results indicate that each of the VIF value is less than the value of the VIF variable which is far below 10. Then it is concluded that there is no multicollinearity between independent variables in the path analysis model.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The results of heteroscedasticity tests show that there is no breach of heteroscedasticity assumptions within the path analysis model.

4.3. Hypothesis Testing

Coefficient Correlation Test

Table 15: Coefficient Correlation Structure II

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.854 ^a	.729	.721	1,21470
a. Predictors: (Constant), Purchase decision, Promotion, Product quality				
b. Dependent Variable: Customer satisfaction				

Source: Processed Data (2018)

Based on the data processing results, The value of R is 0.854, which means that promotion variables, product quality and purchase decision have a very strong correlation with customer satisfaction. The correlation that occurs is a positive coefficient or a very strong correlation, which is between 0.800-1,000.

Determination Coefficient Test

Based on the table of the results the coefficient of determination (RSquare) was 0.729 or 72.9%. This illustrated that the contribution of promotion, product quality and purchasing decision variables, on the fluctuations of customer satisfaction variables is 72.9% and the remaining 27.1% is the contribution of other variables not discussed in this study. (error2 = 0.271).

Overall Simultaneous Test (F Test) Structural II

Table 16: F test Structure II

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	381,392	3	127,131	86,161	.000 ^b
Residual	141,648	96	1,476		
Total	523,040	99			
a. Dependent Variable: Customer satisfaction					
b. Predictors: (Constant), Purchase decision, Promotion, Product quality					

Source: Processed Data (2018)

Based on the results above, the results of the F-count processing was of 86.161. In the F-test table for the 5% significance level and freedom degree of $(n - (k + 1)) = 100 - (3 + 1) = 96$, an Ftable was obtained = 2,699. Because the F count is \geq Ftable or $86.161 \geq 2.699$ and sig F is 0,000, a decision can be drawn to reject H0. This means that there are simultaneous significant effects between promotion, product quality and purchase decision on customer satisfaction on bohemianproject.id products.

Partial Test (t Test) Structure II

Table 17: Path Coefficient and Partial Test (t test) Structure I

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	,525	,717		,733	,465
	Promotion	,123	,055	,185	2,237	,028
	Product quality	,095	,024	,418	4,007	,000
	Purchase decision	,254	,087	,314	2,911	,004

a. Dependent Variable: Customer satisfaction

Source: Processed Data (2018)

Table 18: Variable Correlation Matrix of X1, X2 and Y

Correlations					
		Customer satisfaction	Promotion	Product Quality	Purchase decision
Pearson Correlation	Customer satisfaction	1,000	,723	,819	,807
	Promotion	,723	1,000	,725	,747
	Product quality	,819	,725	1,000	,849
	Purchase decision	,807	,747	,849	1,000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Customer satisfaction	.	,000	,000	,000
	Promotion	,000	.	,000	,000
	Product quality	,000	,000	.	,000
	Purchase decision	,000	,000	,000	.
N	Customer satisfaction	100	100	100	100
	Promotion	100	100	100	100
	Product quality	100	100	100	100
	Purchase decision	100	100	100	100

Source: Processed Data (2018)

Table 19: Direct and Indirect Effects of Promotion (X1), Product quality (X2) Purchase decision (Y) on Customer satisfaction (Z).

Variable	Path coefficient	Direct Effect (%)	Indirect Effect (through), in%			Indirect Effect (%)	total (%)
			X1	X2	Y		
X1	0,185	3,42	-	5,60	4,34	9,95	13,37
X2	0,418	17,43	5,60	-	11,15	16,75	34,18
Y	0,314	9,88	4,34	11,15	-	15,49	25,37
Total							72,9

Source: Processed Data2018

The table above presented the data of effect of each variables such as promotion(X1), product quality (X2) and purchasing decision (Y) on customer satisfaction (Z). The data above shows a significant positive effect on each variable towards the variable of customer satisfaction (Z).

Table 20: Effect Decomposition of Promotion (X1) and Product quality (X2) on Customer satisfaction (Z) through Purchase decision (Y)

Effect of Z through Y	t-count	t-table	Conclusion
$\rho_{zx1} = 0,277 \times 0,314 = 0,0870 = 8,70\%$	2,182	1,96	Significant
$\rho_{zx2} = 0,649 \times 0,314 = 0,2039 = 20,39\%$	2,068	1,96	Significant

Source: Processed Data2018

Therefore, it is stated that all 4 (four) of this study Hypotheses can be answered as follows:

H1. As per early assumption, promotion (X1) has a significant effect on purchase decisions (Y) of Craft products from Bohemian.project.id. Based on the information's above there is a significant positive effect of promotion (X1) on purchase decision (Y). This is because the tcount > ttable value, which rejects H0 or in other words promotion has a significant positive effect on purchase decision. Promotion has a significant effect on purchase decision, in a promotion, a marketing communication process occurs in the form of information transfer, an influencing / persuading so that buyers / consumers are interested and create purchase decision (Tjiptono, 2008: 219).

H2. Based on the study, there is a positive significant effect of product quality (X2) on purchase decision (Y). This is because the t count > t table value, which rejects H0 that means product quality has a positive significant effect on purchase decision. From the results of the study we can see that there is a significant effect of product quality on purchase decision. Product quality has an important role in influencing consumer decisions in purchasing a product. When a customer intends to make a purchase on of a product, they will choose the product which are in terms of quality that will meet their needs / solve their problem. According to Kotler (2014: 84) product quality is the ability of a product or service to demonstrate its function, which is included in the overall durability, reliability, accuracy, ease of operation and repair of the product itself.

H3. Based on the information above, there is a significant positive effect of product quality (X2) on customer satisfaction (Z). For the reason of the tcount > ttable value, which repelled H0 and translated into that promotion has an effect on customer satisfaction. Cannon, Perreault and Mc Carthy (2009: 45) define that product quality is the product's ability to satisfy customer needs or desires. Thus, the product quality is in line to the level of customer satisfaction. Product quality will answer all the perceptions and expectations of the consumers of a product / service. Customer satisfaction is basically a function of expectations and perceptions of the performance of a product/service after customers retain or use the product/services (Sangadji, 2013: 115).

H4. Based on the result above, there is a significant positive effect of promotion (X1) towards customer satisfaction (Z). That is because the tcount > ttable value, which rejects H0 or that purchase decision has an effect on customer satisfaction. Promotion has a significant effect and has an important role in customer satisfaction. Promotion is a form of marketing communication in which highlight the features of the products that will encourage the target to buy it (Kotler, 2014: 41).

5. Discussion

- 1) A significant positive effect of promotion (X1) on purchasing decisions (Y) was found. For the reason of the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ value, which rejects the H_0 or in other words promotion has a significant positive effect on purchase decision. Promotion has a significant effect on purchase decisions, in a promotion, a marketing communication process occurs in the form of information transfer, influencing / persuading buyers / to make the customers interested and ultimately make purchase decisions (Tjiptono, 2008: 219).
- 2) A significant positive effect of product quality (X2) on purchasing decisions (Y) was found. This is because the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ value, which then repels the H_0 or in other words product quality has a positive significant effect on purchase decision. From the results of the study we can see that there is a significant effect of product quality on purchase decision.
- 3) There is a significant positive effect between product quality (X2) on customer satisfaction (Z). this is calculated by the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ value, because H_0 is rejected or in other words promotion has an effect on customer satisfaction. Product quality has a very important role in customer satisfaction. The level of product quality of a company is determined by the level of their customer satisfaction after or while consuming a product from a company.
- 4) There is a significant positive effect of promotion (X1) on customer satisfaction (Z). For the reason of the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ value, rejecting H_0 or in other words the purchase decision affects the customer satisfaction. Promotion has a significant effect and has an important role in customer satisfaction. Promotion is a form of marketing communication in which highlight the features of the product which will persuade the target to buy it (Kotler, 2014: 41).

6. Conclusions and Recommendations

6.1. Conclusions

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion that have been stated above, conclusions shall be taken as follows:

- 1) Promotion has a significant effect on Purchase Decision with a positive direction (+)
- 2) Product quality has a significant effect on Purchase Decision with a positive direction (+)
- 3) Product quality significantly affects on the Customer Satisfaction with a positive direction (+)
- 4) Promotion has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction with a positive direction (+)

6.2. Recommendations

Based on the results of the conclusions regarding the study, the researcher provide the following suggestions:

Suggestions for The Organization

- 1) According to the results of study, promotion has a significant effect on customer satisfaction, so it is advisable to conduct honest promotions therefore customers will feel satisfied in terms of when comparing the advertised product with the reality . In addition, organization should promote various effective advertising media that are favored by the

target market, such as social media to convince customers that these products have the quality, the design, and the excellence that meets the customer expectations.

- 2) Based on the results and observations made, it is recommended to develop experiential marketing strategies.
- 3) Based on the study conducted, product quality has a significant influence on customer satisfaction, the researcher advises the business organization to make an SOP (Standard Operational Procedure) for the production of bohemiant.project.id product accessories so that the quality of goods can be constantly maintained.
- 4) Researcher also advise the organization to improve and develop their human resources which involved in the promotion and selling process, so that promotional opportunities such as maintaining relationships with consumers, social media networking and exhibitions in various domestic regions and abroad can be maximally utilized to increase the value of bohemiant.project.id products.
- 5) The researcher also advise the organization to increase their working capital in order to fulfill the demand and opportunities that are so wide open in today's digital world.
- 6) It is hoped that for further studies, researcher may use larger samples in order produce stronger and more accurate result.
- 7) It is expected for further studies to examine other factors besides promotion, product quality and purchase decision that may have a significant influence on customer satisfaction of craft products from bohemian.project.id, such as marketing mix and other marketing attributes like quality service, product warranty and others.

References

- [1] Cannon, Joseph P, William D. Perreault, Jerome McCarthy. (2009). Pemasaran Dasar Edisi 16 Pendekatan Manajerial Global Buku 2. Jakarta: Penerbit Salemba Empat
- [2] Durianto, Darmadi dkk. (2008). Brand Equity Ten, Strategi Memimpin Pasar. PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama, Jakarta.
- [3] Force (2008). Analysis of Effect of product quality, price and promotion decisions to purchase Nokia Mobile Brands. Journals.
- [4] Ghozali, Imam. (2012). "Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan Program IBM SPSS 20". Semarang: UNDIP.Hawkins, J. 2001. The Creative Economy: How People Make Money from Ideas.Penguins Books, London.
- [5] Kotler, Philip dan Kevin Lane Keller. (2008). Manajemen Pemasaran, Edisi 12, PT Indeks, Jakarta.
- [6] Kotler, Philip dan Gary Armstrong, (2012). Prinsip-prinsip Pemasaran, Erlangga, Jakarta.
- [7] Kotler, Philip. (2014). Manajemen Pemasaran, PT Indeks Kelompok Gramedia, Jakarta.
- [8] Kuncoro, Mudrajad. (2013). "Mudah Memahami dan menganalisis Indikator ekonomi". Yogyakarta: UPP STIM YKPN.
- [9] Malhotra, Naresh K., dan Birks, David F. (2009). Marketing Research An Applied Approach. Second Edition. Prentice Hall.
- [10] Purwanto. (2010). Metodologi Penelitian Kuantitatif untuk Psikologi Pendidikan. Pustaka Pelajar. Yogyakarta.
- [11] Riduwan dan Akdon. (2009). Aplikasi Statistika dan Metode Penelitian untuk Administrasi dan Manajemen. Bandung: Dewa Ruci.
- [12] Schiffman dan Kanuk. (2008). Perilaku konsumen. Edisi 7. Jakarta: Indeks.
- [13] Setiadi, Nugroho. (2010). Perilaku Konsumen: Perspektif Kontemporer pada Motif, Tujuan, dan Keinginan Konsumen, Kencana Prenada Media, Jakarta.
- [14] Sugiyono. (2016). Statistika untuk Penelitian. Cetakan Dua Puluh Tiga. Penerbit Alfabeta. Bandung.

- [15] Sumarwan, Ujang. (2011). Perilaku Konsumen. Bogor: Ghalia Indonesia
- [16] Tjiptono, Fandy. (2008). Strategi pemasaran, Andi Offset, Yogyakarta.
- [17] Rachmad Hidayat (2009). Pengaruh Kualitas Layanan, Product quality Dan Nilai Nasabah Terhadap Kepuasan dan Loyalitas Nasabah Bank Mandiri
- [18] William, J.Stanton. (2004). Prinsip-prinsip Pemasaran, Erlangga, Jakarta.
- [19] Christopher Lovelock, Jochenwitz, Jack Murray. 2012. Pemasaran Jasa Manusia, Teknologi, Strategi: Perspektif Indonesia. Jakarta: Erlangga
- [20] Sangadji, E.M, dan Sopiah 2013. Perilaku Konsumen Pendekatan Praktis Disertai Himpunan Jurnal Penelitian. Yogyakarta; Penerbit Andi
- [21] Kirom, Bahrul. 2015, Mengukur Kinerja Pelayanan dan Kepuasan Konsumen. Bandung: Pustaka Reka Cipta
- [22] Tjiptono Fandy, Ph,D, 2014 , Pemasaran Jasa, Andi, Yogyakarta
- [23] Hawkins, Dell. Best, Roger J dan Coney, Kenneth A 2007. Consumer Behaviour. Newyork L the MCgraw-Hill Companies, Inc.
- [24] Riduwan dan Kuncoro. 2011. Cara Menggunakan Dan Memaknai Path Analysis. Bandung: Alfabeta

*Corresponding author.

E-mail address: Haikalaulia.r@ gmail.com